

ANIMAL USE AND CARE IN COVA DE LES PIXARELLES. AN APPROACH TO BONE PATHOLOGY IN *BOS TAURUS*

Roger Alcàntara Fors^{1,2} Daniel Tonda Carratalà¹ Maria Saña Seguí¹

Bone paleopathology is a good marker of animal use when studying ancient domestic bovine populations. Overexertion, physiological stress and diseases are recorded in the bone and can help determine the involvement of cattle in agricultural and transport tasks and the economic importance of this polyvalent species.

*This work focuses on the remains of *Bos taurus* recovered in Pixarelles cave, a Middle Neolithic site in the northeast of the peninsular territory with an exceptional representation of cattle remains. Examining pathological marks on cattle bones allowed the reconstruction of cattle use and health condition of this early domestic cattle herd.*

Middle Neolithic, Paleopathology, *Bos taurus*, animal management

La paleopatología ósea es un buen marcador del uso de los animales a la hora de estudiar las antiguas poblaciones de bovinos domésticos. El sobreesfuerzo, el estrés fisiológico y las enfermedades quedan registrados en el hueso y pueden ayudar a determinar la implicación del ganado en tareas agrícolas y de transporte, así como la importancia económica de esta especie polivalente.

*Este trabajo se centra en los restos de *Bos taurus* recuperados en la Cova de les Pixarelles, un yacimiento del Neolítico Medio del noreste peninsular con una excepcional representación de restos de ganado vacuno. El examen de las marcas patológicas en los huesos de esta especie permitió reconstruir el uso ganadero y el estado de salud del rebaño vacuno documentado.*

Neolítico Medio, paleopatología, *Bos taurus*, gestión ganadera

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INTRODUCTION

Domestication led to changes in how humans interact with certain animal species, making these increasingly accessible and abundant (Alves *et al.* 2018). As a result of these changes, human communities became increasingly dependent on these animals and developed new means to ensure their long-term survival. Captive breeding and isolating the animals from the natural populations allowed greater control over the animals' development and life. As a result, various techniques and forms of work organisation began to develop, leading to livestock farming. The transition from living free to a captive status is often accompanied by changes in the availability and accessibility of shelter spaces, food and water, and the social

environment (Price 1999). During this transition, a conscious and unconscious selection of the animals that make up the herds occurs. It can vary greatly depending on the characteristics of the environment, the social environment, and the goals and needs of the human groups. The most affected aspects were the activity and mobility patterns and the reproductive and food regimes. Depending on the management of these aspects and the type of livestock exploitation applied, different varieties of animals appeared within the same species (Beaumont *et al.* 2002).

Using animals as a means of work is traditionally related to agriculture, forestry, and environmental management tasks. The main tasks these animals can be involved in are traction and transport (people, material goods, water). Using animals as a means of transport

1.- Laboratori d'Arqueozoologia, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

2.- School of History, Archaeology and Religion. Cardiff University

Corresponding autor: roger.alcantara@uab.cat

and traction implies, in addition to keeping them alive, their specialised training. Ethnographic works show that the training can last between 1 and 3 months, and the animals are used for an average of 5 years for these activities. They usually involve more attentive care and the provision of extraordinary food. Characteristics such as capacity and power must have been relevant for their selection (Watson 1981). To move any object, an animal must exert a force equal to the weight or resistance of that object. The animal selection must consider physical and behavioural attributes, health status, trainability, age, sex, conformation and temperament. In traditional livestock farms, there is a greater tendency to use males than females for agricultural labour, but not exclusively. Bulls are usually trained between the ages of three and four. Before the age of three, bulls have little power, and hard work can influence their growth or cause abnormal bone and muscle development. After four years, animals can be challenging to handle and train since acquired habits must be removed before they can be used (Watson 1981).

The exceptional faunal assemblage of *Bos taurus* recovered at Cova de les Pixarelles (Tavertet, Osona), dated between 3900-3639 cal BC (Alcàntara 2019), has been selected to address if cattle exploitation as a labour force was a common occurrence in the strategies practised by Neolithic groups of the northeast of the peninsular territory. Centred around the consolidation of cattle breeding and management strategies during the Middle Neolithic, this work evaluates whether it is possible to observe the new uses of cattle at an osteological level and demonstrate the exploitation of these animals for intensive agricultural tasks or the transport of heavy loads. At the same time, the palaeopathological evaluation of this remains links to the health conditions of these early herds of domestic cattle, reflecting the potential changes brought about by the animal handling practices of the first farming societies.

MATERIALS

Cova de les Pixarelles opens into the rocky wall that borders the river Riera del Balà to the north, between the town of Tavertet to the west and Morro de l'Abella to the east. The site is at 660 masl, with a vertical drop of 70 meters (Álvarez *et al.* 2016, 2017), contrasting with the "plains" of the immediate upper platform. The location of the cave is characterised by its abrupt and steep orography. The presence of combustion residues linked to cooking activities and food consumption, the smoking of meat, lighting, maintenance and sanitation of the cave characterises the cave's occupation during the Middle Neolithic (Sisa-López de Pablo *et al.* 2022)

The analysed samples come from level XXII, where a total of 456 faunal remains have been studied so far. Of these, 306 were classified as *Bos taurus*, representing 80% of the species documented and a minimum of 7 specimens identified. It is a relatively young population, with no specimens surviving beyond four years. It was possible to identify one individual aged between 1 and 12 months, two individuals between 10 and 12 months, two between 12 and 18 months and two between 42 and 48 months. Considering the sexual dimorphism presented by the species, it was possible to determine that the group would be mainly represented by males, with a few females.

Regarding the anatomical variability, a selection of the meatier upper limb portions and remains of the torso was documented. This recurrence evidences a selection of certain portions with high food value. The comparative analysis carried out with other populations of domestic cattle represented in Early Neolithic sites and with a population of post-palaeolithic *Bos primigenius* shows that the size of Cova de les Pixarelles' cattle is relatively homogeneous with the domestic populations from older sites such as Cueva de Chaves (Huesca) or Cova del Frare (Vallès Occidental). The presence of bone palaeopathology has been evaluated on a total of 207 remains of *Bos taurus*, including all the first, second and third phalanges (n=36), metapodials (n=10), long bones with complete epiphysis (n=50), ribs (n=92) and head bones (n=19).

METHOD

Bone surfaces were analysed macroscopic and microscopically to identify pathologies in the bone. The morphological alterations in the bone were recorded through a formal and photographic description, taking into account the parts of the bone that provide more information for the characterisation and diagnosis of the pathology. The formal description followed three main criteria: location of the pathology, description of the type of alteration observed and stage of development. In the case of osteochondritis dissecans in the talus, the pathology was evaluated following Ruiz (2019). In the case of the phalanges and metapodials, the systematisation published by Bartosiewicz (1997) and later adapted by De Cupere (2000) was strictly followed. Recent notes and modifications proposed by Thomas *et al.* (2021) have been considered in the discussion. The calculation of the Pathological Index (PI) makes it possible to evaluate objectively and systematically the degree of intensity with which the deformation is presented, correlating it with the frequency and intensity of the overexertion the animal was subjected to in life (Bosch *et al.* 2008). Bartosiewicz (1997) describes that the most recurrent affectations in the case of the phalanges are lipping and exostosis. Lipping is defined

Figure 1. Examples of injuries resulting from trauma to the ribs and the development of exostosis during the fusion process.

as an extension of the joint surface, which can develop into bone mass growth at the epiphyses' periphery with the increase in severity of the condition. Exostosis is an overgrowth of bone tissue that develops mainly in the proximal and distal epiphyses. While lipping is a localised affection on the articular surfaces, exostosis is localised more or less homogeneously on the surface of the bone and shows an irregular growth of the bone mass, more or less visible depending on the stage of development (Bartosiewicz 1997). Cases of eburnation, characterised by bone surface wear acquiring a polished appearance, have also been recorded. In the published bibliography, authors use grooving, eburnation or polished aspect indistinctly (Zimmermann 2018; Onar *et al.* 2015; De Cupere 2000; Bartosiewicz 1997; Baker/Brothwell 1980). In the case of the metapodials, five types of bone tissue marks were considered: exostosis, palmar depression, extension of the medial trochlea, proximal lipping and eburnation.

RESULTS

The cattle remains from Cova de les Pixarelles show a significant number of pathological lesions (Tonda 2019). Ten per cent of the remains determined (n=31) have pathologies. Affections are documented mainly in the phalanges (n=11) and ribs (n=12), but also on metapodials (n=3), radii (n=2), talus (n=2) and the mandible (n= 1). The pathologies identified are the result of traumatic injuries, in some cases related to possible infectious processes, and linked to the movement and age of the animal.

Figure 2. Lateral and dorsal view of the mandible with loss of the first molar and scarring of the alveolus.

Traumatic injuries are mainly located in the axial skeleton and, more specifically, in the body of the ribs (Fig. 1). Ribs show trauma in the form of fractures and depressions on the surface of the bone. The most notable cases are two ribs with a severe exostosis (stage 4) developed from the fusion process after the fracture. Likewise, one of the mandibles studied presents an isolated case of mild malformation and ossification of the M1 alveolus (Fig. 2). The animal was between 44-45 months old when it died. The probable cause is a traumatic injury that would cause tooth loss. The impact, the alveolus' ossification and the lack of a first molar could have affected the morphology of the left hemimandible. Despite this, the individual lived on to heal the lost teeth.

Figure 3. Described cases of pathologies in the proximal radius (lipping) and distal radius (pitting), distal metatarsal (widening of the medial trochlea), talus (Osteochondritis dissecans) and first phalanges (lipping and exostosis).

The bone pathologies linked to the animal's movement are in the distal limbs (Fig. 3). In the case of the phalanges, it has been possible to calculate the Pathological Index (PI) on a total of 6 first phalanges. The value obtained is very close to zero, indicating relatively mild effects.

In the case of the first phalanges, nearly 65% of the affectations occur in the posterior section. In the second phalanges, 75% of the affectations are in the anterior section, but they are of greater intensity in the posterior section. Phalange PX1055 is especially noteworthy for its highly developed exostosis. Metapodials show more developed affectations than most phalanges. Metatarsal PX160 stands out with an accentuated extension of the medial trochlea (stage 3) (Fig. 3).

On the other hand, two radii also exhibit some bone modifications. The first corresponds to an animal over 12-15 months old, judging by its state of fusion. The affectations are in the proximal epiphysis. It is a case of lipping (stage 2-3) and exostosis at the periphery of the epiphysis (stage 2). The second corresponds to an animal over 42-48 months old. The affectations are on the distal epiphysis (Fig. 3). It is a series of irregular grooves on the periphery of the surface, identified as pitting (O'Connor 2008: 175; Groot 2005).

Finally, osteochondritis dissecans appears in two right astragali (Figure 3). The development stage is mild-moderate.

The age range of affected specimens varies between 15 and 48 months. Most pathologies concentrate in the extremities (58%), followed by the torso (39%) and

the head (3%). The most documented affectations are lipping and exostosis in the proximal and distal joints (63%), the majority in the distal part (89%). The Pathological Index (PI) has an overall low value, evidencing the mild nature of most of the affectations.

DISCUSSION

Following Bartosiewicz (1997), lipping, exostosis and the extension of the medial trochlea of the metapodials are linked to the overexertion of the animal and are usually considered good indicators of the use of animals as a labour force. The appearance of lipping (Groot 2005; Tell Dahl 2002; De Cupere 2000; Bartosiewicz 2016, 1997) can be one of the best indicators related to the work and overexertion of the animal. On the other hand, it does not need to be an affectation directly and exclusively related to the animal's body size (Bartosiewicz 2008; Bosch *et al.* 2008). Exostosis - proximal and distal - can also be a good indicator of the animal's use during life. This affectation is usually related to chronic inflammation of the joint capsules producing depressions on the palmar surface of the articulation in bones such as the metacarpal and metatarsal. On the other hand, the accumulation of bone material in the dorsal section of metapodials may be linked to an adaptation to traction work. Faced with the abnormal increase in traction force, metacarpals usually develop more severe affectations in the palmar section, while the dorsal will be overloaded by the excessive compression (Onar 2015; Groot 2005;

Seetah 2005; Telldahl 2005; De Cupere 2000; Bartosiewicz 1997, 2006).

Despite being a less frequent affection in the record, the extension of the medial trochlea in metapodials is attributed to overexertion of the animal linked to traction (De Cupere 2000; Bartosiewicz 1997). On the other hand, the asymmetry or deviation in the axis of metapodials, especially in metatarsals, is considered an affection resulting from load-bearing tasks when the animal is still too young, causing injuries in the fusion zone of the epiphysis (Davis 1989; Bartosiewicz 1994; De Cupere 2000). This is a relevant observation since, apart from the work's intensity and duration, the animal's age is also an essential parameter of livestock management strategies (Bartosiewicz 2008; Bosch *et al.* 2008).

However, if we consider the recent proposal of Thomas *et al.* (2021), we need to take a step back. The author argues from the data provided by the herd of feral cattle in Chillingham that some of the overexertion vectors listed so far have a strong correlation with the age of the animals. These are the proximal and distal exostosis of the metatarsus, widening of the metacarpal trochlea, proximal lipping and exostosis of the third phalanx and distal exostosis of the first phalanx. In this sense, the age profile of Cova de les Pixarelles indicates an adult but not an aged population. Therefore, these pathologies are a reminder of the development of an activity that causes significant joint stress and wear, potentially unrelated to the animal's age. However, this same sacrifice profile contravenes the premise of using animals as a labour force traditionally proposed, which involves the survival of the specimens until more advanced ages.

The tendency towards greater affectations in the posterior distal extremities compared to the anterior ones can be related to the data provided by the biostructural and biomechanical studies about the percentage contribution of each limb (anterior and posterior) to the non-physiological effort resulting from the work of load and traction. In load-bearing situations, joints, especially limbs, are subjected to additional stress. In traction activities, the rear section bears excessive stress, and metatarsals and the hip joint are most often deformed, while almost no abnormalities show in the scapula. The pathologies known in the shoulder of cattle are usually traumatic and not arthritic (Bartosiewicz 2008; Groot 2005).

The PI calculation indicates that the herd from Cova de les Pixarelles is a healthy herd (IPI=0.149). The value is lower after the modifications proposed by Thomas *et al.* (2021). The chronologically and spatially closest assemblage for which this value is available corresponds to La Draga site (Bosch *et al.* 2008). In La Draga, a slightly lower pathological index is documented, with bones affected by similar conditions. In the community of La Draga, this spe-

cies was involved in transporting wood. However, traumatic injuries such as those observed in the ribs are not documented.

Affectations to the ribs (40%) are related to physical trauma: fractures due to blunt impacts, falls, and other events that could cause injuries of this type. If we consider the orography of the area, it is not surprising that the herd's movement through the territory could have caused more than one fall and the consequent injury. This issue is possibly an important clue for understanding the management and use of animals in Cova de les Pixarelles. The biomechanical study of the first phalanges (Alcàntara 2019) proposed a relatively high activity level for this herd related to its mobility through the steep territory surrounding the site. The greater physical demand and wear associated with this mobility pattern could also explain the presence of pathologies linked to overexertion and the early appearance of pathologies correlated with the animal's age.

Finally, the survival of individuals beyond the moment of trauma (allowing partial or total healing) supports particular attention to the well-being and survival of animals (Tonda 2019). It is also a manifesto of accumulated knowledge and well-established livestock practices during the Middle Neolithic northeast of the Iberian peninsula.

CONCLUSIONS

Cattle exploitation in Cova de les Pixarelles is centred on their meat value, as indicated by factors such as skeletal variability and the ages at which the animals were killed. There is a recurrence of the skeletal portions richest in biomass (humerus-radius-ulna and pelvis-femur-tibia), and animals are most represented around 24 months when they are at their meat optimum (Alcàntara *et al.* 2017).

Although the topography of the territory could have played a significant role in defining the intensity of the physical activity developed by these animals, the presence of some pathologies linked to overexertion allow us to consider their potential use in loading, traction or transport, such as the transfer of material from one point to another. The presence of few affected animals aligns with the traditional management and use of individuals selected as a workforce, which is why meat exploitation is better represented than animal power. Some of the injuries can also be related to accidents and not exclusively to the use of the animal. The study of the remaining faunal bone fragments recovered in Cova de les Pixarelles could provide new data regarding the exploitation and use of cattle.

Bone pathology is a good indicator of the animal's state of health. By registering and studying the effects

on the bone, we can identify the animal's use in life and differentiate between different uses and selective pressures.

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